

Community Metabolic Modeling Unlocks the Potential of Thermophilic Synthetic Communities for Enhanced Butyric Acid Production

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1 **Abstract**

2 The intricate network of interspecies interactions within microbial communities drives their
3 functional organization, enabling them to perform complex tasks like breaking down resistant
4 lignocellulosic materials into volatile fatty acids (VFAs). Butyric acid (BA), a VFA, is
5 gaining attention for its applications in sustainable aviation fuel, polymers, fibers, and
6 cosmetics. However, the need for costly enzymatic pre-treatment of lignocellulosic substrates
7 limits the economic viability of a biosustainable production process. This study
8 experimentally demonstrated the effectiveness of a mutualistic co-culture of thermophilic
9 bacteria *Clostridium thermocellum* and *Clostridium thermobutyricum* in converting
10 lignocellulose to BA without enzymatic pre-treatment. Despite >100% enhancement in
11 substrate utilization compared to mono-culture, significant carbohydrates and fermentation
12 byproducts remained unused. Using high-quality, manually curated genome-scale metabolic
13 models (GEMs), the metabolic interactions within the co-culture were characterized, and
14 bottlenecks that contribute to incomplete substrate utilization were identified. This research
15 highlights the potential of co-cultures and synthetic communities in sustainable
16 bioproduction.

17 Introduction

18 Bacterial communities are ubiquitous in nature, forming elaborate relationships and
19 interactions that enable them to perform tasks unattainable by single members (Zuñiga *et al.*,
20 2020, Coker *et al.*, 2022). One such task involves the breakdown of plant-derived material
21 into volatile fatty acids (VFAs), including acetic, lactic, and butyric acid (BA) (Agnihotri *et al.*
22 *et al.*, 2022). BA is a particularly valuable fermentation product because of its widespread use
23 as a versatile platform chemical in the food and pharmaceutical industry. BA holds immense
24 potential as a precursor for various applications, such as fiber production, polymer synthesis,
25 as well as production of cosmetics, and aviation fuels (Linger *et al.*, 2020; Salvachúa *et al.*,
26 2021). Currently, BA is primarily synthesized from petroleum, which is not only costly but
27 also not sustainable.

28 Numerous bioprocesses have been suggested for utilizing renewable substrates from
29 lignocellulosic sources to produce VFA, including BA (Linger *et al.*, 2020; Salvachúa *et al.*,
30 2021). However, these processes commonly depend on single microorganisms and
31 necessitate biomass preprocessing steps using enzymatic, chemical, and/or mechanical
32 deconstruction strategies, which are often costly and have diminished yields (Chen *et al.*,
33 2014). To tackle this challenge, a novel approach for BA bioproduction has been proposed,
34 utilizing a synthetic thermophilic bacterial co-culture. This approach involves the close
35 interaction of the two thermophilic bacteria *Clostridium thermocellum* DSM1313 (CTC) and
36 *Clostridium thermobutyricum* DSM4928 (CTB). CTC has gained attention for its remarkable
37 proficiency in effectively breaking down insoluble and oligomeric lignocellulosic substrates,
38 owing to a highly specialized multi-enzyme apparatus known as the cellulosome (Lamed *et al.*
39 *et al.*, 1983; Hirano *et al.*, 2016). This intricate structure found in several anaerobic bacteria
40 such as *Bacteroides*, *Clostridium*, and *Ruminococcus* (Doi *et al.*, 2003) comprises primary
41 and secondary scaffolding proteins, serving as anchoring point for a wide variety of
42 hydrolytic enzymes, including cellulases, hemicellulases, and pectinases. On the other hand,
43 CTB demonstrates high efficiency in converting a wide range of monomeric carbohydrates
44 into BA (Wiegel *et al.*, 1989). When combined as co-culture, CTC and CTB can effectively
45 convert lignocellulosic substrates into BA in a single-step process, bypassing the costly and
46 inefficient preprocessing step (Chi *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, such consolidated
47 bioprocessing for production of VFA at elevated temperatures has been demonstrated to offer
48 advantages and cost-effectiveness (Hao & Wang, 2015). Thus, this thermophilic and
49 effective co-culture offers a promising approach for the sustainable production of BA as an
50 industrially relevant chemical.

51 Constraint-based metabolic modeling is a powerful tool in systems biology that offers a
52 comprehensive understanding of the metabolism of individual microorganisms, i.e.
53 metabolic models or M-models, as well as microbial communities, i.e. community metabolic
54 models, CM-models. These genome-scale metabolic models (GEMs) are reconstructions of
55 the entire metabolic network of a cell, incorporating all biochemical and multi-omics
56 information available for a specific microbe and allowing for a detailed mechanistic

57 understanding of metabolic processes (Bordbar *et al.*, 2014; Kumar *et al.*, 2019). GEMs can
58 accurately predict a multitude of functional states of a cell, providing valuable insights into
59 the metabolic and production capabilities of microorganisms. Expanding this framework to
60 communities has demonstrated unprecedented capabilities in unraveling the complex and
61 dynamic interactions of multiple microbes (Zengler *et al.*, 2018; Zuñiga *et al.*, 2019;
62 Zaramela *et al.*, 2021).

63 Here, a CTC-CTB corn stover to BA system was established and experimentally
64 characterized, including the substrate utilization and product formation capacity of mono-
65 and co-cultures. Comprehensive GEMs for CTC (iGL735) and CTB (iGL834) were
66 subsequently constructed. Additionally, these individual models were integrated into a highly
67 curated CM-model (iGL²1559). The modeling framework was employed to unveil
68 interactions and provide a mechanistic insight into BA production from lignocellulosic
69 substrates, paving the way for the development of a thermophilic and sustainable bioprocess
70 based on a synthetic CTC-CTB co-culture.

71 **Results**

72 **Reconstruction and refinement of the individual M-models for two thermophilic** 73 **anaerobes**

74 An initial version of a GEM of CTC was constructed using as a foundation the most recent
75 metabolic reconstruction of this organism (*i*CBI655, Garcia *et al.*, 2020) and its genome
76 annotation. Additionally, the first reported GEM for *C. thermobutyricum* (CTB) was
77 constructed, leveraging the annotated genome information alongside highly curated M-
78 models from other closely related species, including the previously developed CTC model,
79 and models for *Clostridium ljungdahlii* (*i*HN637, Nagarahan *et al.*, 2013), *Bacillus subtilis*
80 (*i*YO844, Oh *et al.*, 2007; *i*JT964-ME, Tibochoa-Bonilla *et al.*, 2022), and *Escherichia coli*
81 (*i*EC1515, Monk *et al.*, 2017), as well as protein sequence homology (Fig. 1A, Top).

82 To ensure the fidelity and robustness of our reconstructions, both M-models underwent an
83 iterative process of manual curation and refinement. This curation led to the introduction of
84 various modifications, spanning aspects such as mass and energy equilibrium adjustments,
85 rectifying cofactor discrepancies, standardizing biomass metabolites among models,
86 updating and repairing gene-reaction associations, broadening permissible metabolite
87 exchanges, resolving infeasible flux cycles, and introducing or removing various metabolic
88 reactions (See Methods) (Fig. 1A, Bottom).

89 For both organisms, the metabolic network was partitioned into two distinct compartments,
90 the cytoplasm and the extracellular space. Additionally, a specialized compartment
91 representing the cellulosome was defined for CTC. This unique compartment serves as a
92 model of the fundamental enzymatic activities crucial for breaking down cellulose,
93 hemicellulose, and other intricate polysaccharides. While the structure outlined in the M-
94 model offers a generalized portrayal of CTC's mechanisms for degrading complex
95 carbohydrates, it is important to acknowledge that due to lack of information, the cellulosome
96 reconstruction might not fully capture the complete array of enzymes and specific processes
97 employed in nature by this microorganism (Hirano *et al.*, 2016).

98 The completed M-model for CTC, designated as *i*GL735, comprises 735 genes, 733
99 metabolites, and 780 reactions, covering 26.3% of the genome. The final M-model for CTB
100 (*i*GL834) is composed of 834 genes, 790 metabolites, and 876 reactions, offering 27.2% of
101 genomic coverage (Fig. 1B). A comparison between the generated GEMs and the various
102 templates employed for their construction is presented in Table 1.

103 **Building and evaluating a two-member CM-model**

104 Subsequently, the individual M-models were merged to create a CM-model. These models
105 offer a mathematical representation of the genomic and metabolic attributes of the
106 microorganisms within a community, serving as essential instruments for investigating the
107 metabolic interplay and synergies that emerge in shared environments. By amalgamating the
108 separately constructed M-models of CTC and CTB, a two-member CM-model was

109 formulated. The model operates on the principle of a compartmentalized community,
110 envisioning a scenario where various members reside within a common compartment and
111 engage in the use and exchange of a shared metabolites pool (SMP) (Nagarajan *et al.*, 2013;
112 Klitgord & Segrè, 2010). Within this framework, every nutrient and by-product generated by
113 any individual member becomes accessible for consumption by all other participants in the
114 community. This setup helps to model dynamic ecosystems where metabolic interactions
115 occur seamlessly. At its core, the CM-model focuses on a linear objective, which involves
116 the summation of biomass fluxes attributed to each organism within the community. This
117 linear objective can be tuned to represent the different proportions in which each member is
118 present and serves as a quantitative measure of the collective growth and productivity of the
119 entire community, encapsulating the cumulative contributions of individual members (Fig.
120 1C).

121 Considering the metabolic exchange capacities of each member within the community, the
122 SMP underwent meticulous manual curation. The resulting CM-model, designated as
123 *iGL²1559*, accounts for two organisms, totaling 1,559 genes and engaging in 1,777 reactions
124 involving 1,679 metabolites, 37 of which are shared through the SMP (Fig. 1D). Each
125 individual anaerobe possesses distinct metabolic pathways and functionalities inherent to its
126 genetic and biochemical makeup. These variances underscore the unique metabolic roles
127 played by each member, contributing to the collective functionality of the co-culture (Fig.
128 1E).

129 **Establishing growth rates of individual consortium members from complex** 130 **lignocellulosic biomass substrates**

131 A comprehensive set of evaluations were conducted, both *in vivo* and *in silico*, to assess the
132 performance of CTC and CTB both individually and as a consortium on complex carbon
133 substrates, with a particular emphasis on a significant source derived from agricultural waste:
134 deacetylated and mechanically refined corn stover (DMR). DMR is a complex composition
135 solid resulting from applying mild alkaline and further mechanical refining treatments to corn
136 stover solids (Chen *et al.*, 2016). It primarily comprises a blend of cellulose, a homopolymer
137 of glucose units (referred here as glucans), hemicellulose, a heteropolymer primarily
138 composed of xylose units (referred here as xylans), and lignin, a heteropolymer composed of
139 aromatic monomeric units. These long chain carbohydrate polymers are neither soluble nor
140 fermentable; hence, the monomeric units must be liberated for utilization. The average
141 composition of the DMR carbohydrate fraction consists in a ratio of 3:1 glucan to xylan. This
142 ratio was employed to set up the initial composition of the growth media used by the models.
143 Although other polymeric carbohydrates like galactans and arabinans are also present in
144 DMR, their proportions are relatively small and were hence not considered in the modeling
145 (Fig. 2A).

146 Experimental results confirmed that CTC externally decomposes and hydrolyzes both
147 cellulose and hemicellulose present in DMR solids, resulting in a significant buildup of

148 soluble carbohydrates in the medium (Fig. 2B). This leftover supernatant, termed DMR
149 liquor, is rich in free carbohydrate oligomers, particularly xylans and glucans, that were
150 liberated but not consumed by CTC. Among these DMR solids decomposition by-products,
151 CTC demonstrates a preference for assimilation of soluble cellulose-hydrolysis oligomers,
152 specifically glucans. It has been previously described that the length of the glucan chain that
153 CTC is able to assimilate ranges from two (cellobiose) to six (cellohexaose) glucose units
154 (Zhang & Lynd, 2005) (Fig. 2B and 2E). Conversely, CTC exhibits an inability to assimilate
155 pentose-based polymers derived from hemicellulose breakdown (xylans) (Fig. 2B). Notably,
156 despite possessing a xylose transporter, CTC's consumption pathway for xylose is
157 incomplete, lacking the enzymes xylose isomerase (XylA or Xi) and xylulokinase (XylB or
158 Xk), both crucial for integrating this carbon source into the metabolic network through the
159 pentose phosphate pathway. Additionally, CTC shows limited to no growth on monomeric
160 hexoses like galactose and fructose or pentoses such as arabinose (Supplementary Table 1)
161 (Verbeke *et al.*, 2017). In contrast, CTB demonstrates consumption capabilities across
162 various soluble carbohydrates, encompassing simple mono- and dimeric hexoses like
163 cellobiose and glucose, as well as monomeric pentoses, i.e. xylose, both supplemented
164 individually or as a complex mixture in the form of DMR liquor (Fig. 2C and 2E).

165 The benefit of utilizing a co-culture setup lies in the synergistic effect between its members.
166 Experiments have shown that the CTC-CTB co-culture can adapt to new conditions (Fig.
167 2D), exemplified here by the ability to accomplish growth on insoluble complex
168 carbohydrates and achieving increased substrate consumption compared to mono-culture
169 setups. However, co-culture setup leads to the emergence of new metabolic interactions,
170 which are challenging to identify by experimental setups alone. CM-models offer the
171 advantage of easily predicting the individual growth and metabolic requirements of each
172 member under various conditions, thereby elucidating the metabolic interactions within the
173 community.

174 The CM-model *iG²1777* was used to effectively predict the growth phenotypes of CTC and
175 CTB under both mono- and co-culture conditions (Fig. 2F). Simulation results indicated a
176 notable reduction in growth rate for CTC in co-culture conditions, averaging approximately
177 90%, particularly in the presence of hexoses in the media, i.e. cellobiose, as well as in solid
178 DMR. Additionally, CTC exhibited no growth on xylose (monomeric pentose) either
179 individually or as part of the co-culture. Conversely, CTB showed only a slight decrease in
180 growth rate in co-culture when consuming cellobiose and no decrease when utilizing xylose.
181 An intriguing observation arose during simulations involving DMR as sole substrate. It was
182 revealed that CTB did not exhibit individual growth due to its limited capacity to degrade
183 complex carbohydrate polymers. However, as part of a co-culture, CTB experienced
184 significant growth by leveraging the available free carbohydrates hydrolyzed by CTC. It is
185 important to emphasize that the observed synergistic effect, enabling CTB growth in a
186 complex lignocellulosic substrate, is accompanied by a significant decrease in the growth of
187 CTC.

188 **The CM-model forecasts the metabolic capabilities of the butyric acid-producing**
189 **consortium**

190 To provide valuable insights into the metabolic pathways and fermentation profiles of the
191 consortium, both *in silico* characterization and experimental measurements of the primary
192 fermentation by-products excreted by the two microbes (axenically and as co-culture) using
193 DMR as a substrate were conducted (Supplementary Fig. 1). Predicted fermentation profiles
194 were consistent with the products measured experimentally. Observations revealed that CTC
195 undergoes mixed-acid fermentation, with formic and acetic acid (FA, AA, correspondingly)
196 as well as ethanol (Etoh) identified as the main detected end-products, albeit in varying
197 proportions (0.5, 4.0, and 1.2 g L⁻¹ respectively) (Fig. 3A). Conversely, considerable amounts
198 of BA (8.0 g L⁻¹) as well as AA (2.0 g L⁻¹) were measured as fermentation products for CTB
199 (Fig. 3B). Finally, the co-culture produced a mix of all four fermentation products, though in
200 different proportions compared to individual growth (FA 0.5 g L⁻¹, Etoh 2.6 g L⁻¹, AA 3.1 g
201 L⁻¹, BA 2.7 g L⁻¹) (Fig. 3C). Additionally, simulations predicted that in all tested scenarios,
202 both anaerobes excrete an extra series of common end-products, including CO₂, H₂, H⁺, and
203 H₂O (not experimentally measured) (Fig. 3D).

204 CM-model simulations also revealed that the consortium engages in the exchange of AA,
205 Etoh (from CTC to CTB) (Fig. 3E), as well as a diverse array of amino acids (AAs) (Fig. F).
206 A total of 17 AAs, including proline, serine, and valine, were exchanged, with 80% being
207 produced in excess by CTB and transferred to CTC. Previous reports have documented
208 excretion of AAs into the media by CTC (Yayo *et al.*, 2023), however, no studies exist
209 indicating AAs excretion by CTB or the fate of these AAs as public goods, supporting the
210 idea that metabolic exchanges play a crucial role in optimizing and maximizing growth and
211 production within microbial communities. Similar examples of AAs transfer among members
212 have been reported for other communities (Zengler *et al.*, 2018; Zuñiga *et al.*, 2019; Zuñiga
213 *et al.*, 2021).

214 By contrasting the activity across various subsystems under mono- and co-culture conditions,
215 the metabolic functions of each member can be uncovered (Fig. 3F), unveiling a clear
216 division of labor influenced by the distinct metabolic capacities of each participant. CTC acts
217 as the degrader of polymers and supplier of raw materials and building blocks (xylose and
218 AA), while CTB produces high-value compounds (BA and AAs). Nevertheless, the co-
219 culture unveiled synergistic capabilities absent in axenic growth, enabling the microbes to
220 surmount metabolic constraints and flourish in environments where the mono-cultures
221 exhibit diminished performance, as demonstrated in DMR conditions with CTB suggesting
222 a syntrophic relationship withing this community.

223 **Exploring the interplay between acetic and butyric acid: Insights from CM-model flux**
224 **dynamics**

225 As previously noted, *iGL*²¹⁵⁵⁹ predicts the exchange of AA and potentially Etoh among the
226 community members, particularly being utilized by CTB. However, experimental data and
227 *in silico* simulations have confirmed CTB's incapability to thrive solely on AA or Etoh as a
228 carbon source (Supplementary Table 1). The involvement of AA in CTB's BA production
229 has been documented previously (Canganella *et al.*, 2002). A similar mechanism has also
230 been observed in various BA-producing microbes, including bacteria found in the human gut
231 (Louis & Flint, 2009). Simulations carried out by *iGL*²¹⁵⁵⁹ revealed a significant alteration
232 in the pathway and flux distribution of the BA production system upon the introduction of
233 AA into the medium (Fig. 4A and 4B). By quantifying the metabolic fluxes across this
234 system, it was observed that in the absence of AA, the metabolic flux of the acetyl-CoA pool
235 is divided between AA and BA production (22% and 63% respectively), with 100% of BA
236 production facilitated by the Buttk enzyme (Fig. 4A). Contrary, it was forecasted that the
237 activity across the butyryl-CoA/acetate CoA transferase (Coat) reaction contributes
238 approximately 78% of the total flux directed towards BA synthesis when AA is introduced.
239 This suggests that AA serves as an essential building block, facilitating the extension of the
240 carbon chain for the synthesis of longer-chain compounds such as BA, rather than primarily
241 being utilized for biomass generation (Fig. 4B). Previous radiolabeled carbon assays
242 demonstrated that at least 50% of BA originates from AA (Canganella *et al.*, 2002), with up
243 to 85% in butyrate-producing gut bacteria (Macfarlane & Macfarlane, 2003).
244 Additionally, through evaluations of the co-culture, it was observed experimentally and *in*
245 *silico* that introducing diverse concentrations of AA into the system leads to a notable rise in
246 BA production (Fig. 4C and 4D). Not only was there an increase in the final BA titer
247 measured, but also in the production rate. This phenomenon has been previously documented
248 for CTB in axenic growth (Canganella *et al.*, 2002), but not as part of a consortium. On the
249 contrary, simulations showed a metabolic trade off in which AA utilization led to a reduced
250 growth rate (Fig. 4E). Previous studies observed a growth enhancement of 15% in CTB
251 mono-culture upon AA supplementation (Canganella *et al.*, 2002) but no studies of growth
252 in co-culture have been reported. This implies that this process depends on additional
253 environmental factors, triggering a switch between alternative pathways in response to media
254 alterations. Incorporating these constraints into the computational model requires a more
255 thorough experimental characterization and understanding of these regulatory mechanisms.
256 Simulations also indicated that Etoh (C2) could putatively serve as an elongation precursor
257 for increased BA production, with the added benefit of not affecting growth (Fig. 4B and
258 4E). Although the CTB genome encodes a putative bifunctional alcohol dehydrogenase to
259 convert Etoh into AA, its functional activity remains uncertain, and there is currently no
260 conclusive experimental evidence regarding CTB's ability to uptake Etoh (Fig. 4C).

261 **Discussion**

262 The findings presented in this study shed light on the intricate dynamics of microbial
263 communities and their metabolic capabilities in the context of bioconversion of renewable
264 substrates. One of the key observations is the complementary role played by different
265 members of the community. The presence of CTB fills the void left by CTC's inability to
266 exploit xylans and other carbohydrates, thus allowing for single-step BA production and
267 improved biomass conversion.

268 The distinctive metabolic capabilities of both CTC and CTB highlight their adaptation to
269 mixed syntrophic growth. On one hand, CTC's ability to hydrolyze hemicellulose (rich in
270 xylan) while showing no consumption of xylose suggests efficient access to cellulose as an
271 energy source. Simultaneously, it facilitates the growth of other microorganisms by providing
272 essential substrates, in exchange for other high value molecules like amino acids, which CTC
273 can benefit from. On the other hand, evidence from both phylogenetic studies (Louis *et al.*,
274 2007) and radioisotope analyses (Duncan *et al.*, 2004) indicates the prevalence of the Coat
275 route in butyrate-producing bacteria. This underscores the significance of AA and its ability
276 to modulate metabolic responses in organisms from diverse ecosystems.

277 A significant aspect of the metabolic pathways of both CTC and CTB, akin to many other
278 Clostridia, is the reliance on ferredoxins as electron acceptors for energy production (Guerrini
279 *et al.*, 2008). The activity within ferredoxin systems has been observed to govern energy
280 production, fermentation profiles, and product exchange patterns. For instance, simulating an
281 increase in the flux within ferredoxin systems results in an excessive production of reduced
282 energy intermediates like NADH, prompting a preference for excreting less oxidized
283 compounds such as formic acid and H₂. Conversely, limiting the flux decreases the cellular
284 redox potential, leading to a decrease in fermentation products (such as butyrate) and an
285 increase in the excretion of CO₂, a highly oxidized carbon molecule. These findings
286 underscore the regulatory significance of ferredoxin-mediated redox reactions in these
287 organisms. While the fermentation profiles predicted by the *iGL*²1559 CM-model were
288 consistent with *in vivo* measurements, our study did identify discrepancies in growth rates
289 when compared to experimental data. These differences highlight the intricate nature of
290 microbial community dynamics and offer valuable insights for further refining our modeling
291 techniques to better understand and accurately represent these complex interactions.

292 Experimental evidence indicates that the co-culture arrangement exhibits increased substrate
293 consumption, achieving a substantial biomass deconstruction rate of 84%, in contrast to their
294 individual axenic cultures, this represents >100 % enhancement in substrate utilization.
295 Despite the augmented substrate utilization and potential synergies in the co-culture there is
296 room for further optimization, residual glucose and xylose oligomers remain at the end of the
297 growth phase, alongside arabinan and galactan residues (Fig. 5A). It is worth noting that
298 besides carbohydrates, significant amounts of AA (3.1 g L⁻¹) and Etoh (2.6 g L⁻¹) remain as
299 well, with the quantity of AA comparable to the final BA titer (2.7 g L⁻¹) (Fig.s 3C and 5A).

300 As mentioned, these residual C2 compounds could potentially be recycled and utilized for
301 chain elongation of BA or other valuable VFAs.

302 These bottlenecks suggest an opportunity for further refinement and optimization of BA
303 production. Based on our observations, several factors were identified that could contribute
304 to these constraints (Fig. 5B). First, there might be competition for shared resources, thus
305 growth of one organism would hinder the growth of the other. Model simulations revealed
306 that CTB exhibits a greater carbon uptake, suggesting a potential competitive advantage over
307 CTC. Product inhibition may be another constraint, this VFA may primarily affect the growth
308 and activity of CTC. Conversely, accumulation of Etoh or AA may inhibit CTB, as
309 previously reported (Canganella *et al.*, 2002). Another potential issue restraining the system
310 is the limitation of the overall degrading capability of the cellulosome. The enzymes in the
311 cellulosome system may become saturated and inhibited when exposed to elevated
312 carbohydrate concentrations, which are unlikely to be encountered in the natural environment
313 of CTC. Additionally, it is possible that the array of enzymes present in CTC's cellulosome
314 may not efficiently cleave the full range of carbohydrate oligomers configurations present in
315 DMR. Further studies are required to identify the specific enzymes needed for efficient
316 cleavage of all carbohydrate diversity of this complex substrate.

317 It may be possible to exploit all these residual substrates using specific pathways not found
318 in the CTC-CTB co-culture. Although some molecular tools for these organisms exist
319 (Mearls *et al.*, 2015; Riley *et al.*, 2019; Walker *et al.*, 2019) they are scarce, and their
320 development and implementation require considerable time and effort. An effective and
321 viable approach to overcome these bottlenecks entails augmenting the current co-culture
322 through the introduction of additional microbes that harmonize with the existing setup. These
323 new additions should possess the requisite metabolic pathways for producing BA from the
324 residual carbohydrates or fermentation products of the current setup. Augmentation of the
325 co-culture can be achieved by two approaches: targeted and untargeted augmentation (Fig.
326 5C). The first necessitates thorough bibliographic or database exploration and leveraging
327 CM-model guidance to pinpoint microbial strains with well-characterized attributes that align
328 with the desired requirements. Conversely, untargeted augmentation involves the isolation
329 and screening of microbes possessing favorable metabolic characteristics. Addressing these
330 challenges requires a deeper understanding of the community interactions and the
331 implementation of strategies leading to the augmentation of new members to the consortium.
332 The utilization of co-cultures, defined consortia, and complex synthetic communities in
333 conjunction with lignocellulosic biomass as a renewable substrate presents a promising
334 alternative to conventional production of VFAs using petroleum-based precursors. This
335 approach not only offers environmental benefits but also holds economic promise for the
336 sustainable obtention of other valuable compounds.

337 **Materials and methods**

338 **Individual GEM model construction and refinement**

339 The corresponding genome sequences of *C. thermocellum* and *C. thermobutyricum* were
340 downloaded from the NCBI website: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/CP002416> and
341 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/LTAY000000000>, respectively. The GEM of *C.*
342 *thermocellum* (i.e. *iCBI655*, Garcia *et al.*, 2020) was obtained from:
343 [https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fbioe.2020.00772/full#supplementary-](https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fbioe.2020.00772/full#supplementary-material)
344 [material](https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fbioe.2020.00772/full#supplementary-material). The most up-to-date and complete GEMs of *C. ljungdahlii* (i.e. *iHN637*, Nagarahan
345 *et al.*, 2013), *B. subtilis* (i.e. *iYO844*, Oh *et al.*, 2007; *iJT964-ME*, Tibochoa-Bonilla *et al.*,
346 2022), and *E. coli* (i.e. *iEC1515*, Monk *et al.*, 2017) were downloaded from the BiGG
347 database (<http://bigg.ucsd.edu/>) (King *et al.*, 2016) and provided as template models. These
348 models were selected due to their high level of curation and extensive biological data support.
349 An initial draft of the individual GEMs of *C. thermocellum* and *C. thermobutyricum* was
350 generated using the RAVEN Toolbox package (Ver. 2.9.2) (Wang *et al.*, 2018) for
351 MATLAB. For the draft generation, the library uses a bidirectional homology search via
352 BLASTp with the original genomes and the template models, assigning the best-fitting Gene-
353 Protein-Reaction (GPR) rule. The RAVEN Toolbox function `getModelFromHomology()`
354 was executed with the following cut-off parameters: a maximum E-value of 50, a minimum
355 alignment length of 90 residues, and a minimum identity of 40%. For missing gene
356 identifications, NCBI BLASTp was manually performed with the above parameters. To
357 ensure quality control, drafts were subjected to iterative manual curation using the
358 COntstraint-Based Reconstruction and Analysis (COBRApy) (Ver. 0.29) (Ebrahim *et al.*,
359 2013), a Python software suite for quantitative analysis of biochemical networks. The
360 remaining annotated genes were included in the model by gap filling with the help of the
361 databases UNIPROT, BiGG (King *et al.*, 2016), KEGG (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2023), and MetaCyc
362 (Caspi *et al.*, 2014). Reactions were verified with experimental data when available, such as
363 for the BA synthesis pathway (Wiegel *et al.*, 1989). For reactions with no specific data
364 available, information from the previously used template models was utilized. To aid in the
365 gap filling and benchmarking process, relevant pathways and metabolic subsystems were
366 visualized using the library Escher (Ver. 1.7.1) (King *et al.*, 2015). To ensure standardized
367 nomenclature and facilitate comparison between other GEMs, all reactions and metabolites
368 in the model were named with BiGG IDs. Cellular transport systems, particularly
369 carbohydrate uptake and amino acid transport reactions, were meticulously verified or
370 rectified. Each metabolite in the extracellular space compartment was assigned an exchange
371 reaction, although uptake may be restricted depending on the composition of the growth
372 media. The biomass reaction included all essential constituents such as carbohydrates, lipids,
373 co-factors, and vitamins, as well as their fractions in the biomass composition. For CTC, the
374 biomass equation derived from model *iCBI655* was used. Due to the lack of a detailed

375 biomass composition for CTB, the macromolecular composition of *C. ljungdahlii*
376 represented in the model *iHN637* was used as a reference.

377 **Community metabolic model (CM-model) generation**

378 The generation of CM-models was carried out using COBRAPy, employing a
379 compartmentalized strategy. Initially, the individual GEMs of CTC and CTB were both
380 placed within a unique common compartment, forming sub-partitions and a Shared
381 Metabolite Pool (SMP). This pool allows the interconnection of individual metabolic
382 networks and the allocation of extracellular resources, based on the uptake capabilities of
383 each network. The SMP was populated with metabolites in line with the existing data from
384 the individual GEMs of CTC and CTB. To distinguish common elements, prefixes
385 corresponding to each organism were appended to each internal metabolite (i.e.
386 glucose_CTC, glucose_CTB) and reaction (i.e. POR_CTC, POR_CTB) within the metabolic
387 network. In the case of CTC, the suffix _CL was added to denote reactions that incorporated
388 the cellulosome system compartment. The objective function was set to maximize biomass
389 reactions from each individual model.

390 **Model simulations and constrains**

391 Individual GEM and CM-model simulations were conducted using the COBRA Toolbox
392 with the Gurobi Optimizer (Version 5.6.3, Gurobi Optimization Inc., U.S.A) as the solver.
393 The maximal growth rate was simulated using the Flux Balance Analysis (FBA)-associated
394 algorithm OptCom, which aims to maximize biomass reactions. For the community, the
395 population's growth rate was determined by the cumulative fluxes through the biomass
396 reactions of the individual models, as shown in equation 1:

$$397 \quad Model_{Objective} = Flux_{Biomass_a} + Flux_{Biomass_b} + \dots \quad (eq. 1)$$

398 Simulations in different carbohydrates were executed by constraining the carbon source
399 uptake to a maximum of 10 mmol gDW⁻¹ h⁻¹. For DMR, this amount was allocated in a ratio
400 of 7.5 mmol gDW⁻¹ h⁻¹ for glucose and 2.5 mmol gDW⁻¹ h⁻¹ xylose. No constraints were
401 applied to the default exchange capabilities of the individual members, with all transporters
402 being open and free to exchange. The total metabolic flux for each organism subsystem was
403 calculated using the formula in equation 2:

$$404 \quad Subsystem_Flux_{k,j} = \sum_{i=1}^n Flux_{i,k,j} \quad (eq. 2)$$

405 The equation indicates that the total flux for a community member specific subsystem (*k, j*)
406 is the sum of the individual fluxes corresponding to that subsystem. For simulations involving
407 acetic acid and ethanol, the presence and assimilation of these compounds were achieved by

408 fixing the total uptake of these two molecules to 5 mmol gDW⁻¹ h⁻¹. The flux was then
409 distributed to achieve the desired proportions, maximizing the biomass growth of both
410 community members simultaneously.

411 **Strains, maintenance, and seed cultures preparation**

412 *Clostridium thermocellum* (DSM 1313) and *Clostridium thermobutyricum* (ATCC 49875)
413 were obtained from the Leibniz Institute DSMZ - German Collection of Microorganisms and
414 Cell Cultures GmbH and the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), respectively. The
415 strains were revived under anaerobic conditions by rehydrating the pellet with 0.25 mL of
416 culture media, then transferring the contents to a culture tube containing 5 mL of medium.
417 From this primary culture, 2.5 mL was inoculated into each of two serum bottles containing
418 25 mL of culture media. These serum bottles were incubated anaerobically at 55 °C for 24-
419 48 hours, with OD measurements taken to monitor growth. Subsequently, 0.5 mL aliquots of
420 cultures in the exponential phase were mixed with 0.5 mL of an autoclaved mixture of 10%
421 glycerol and 10% dimethyl sulfoxide and stored at -80 °C in sealed vials. For seed culture
422 preparation, glycerol stocks were thawed, and 0.2 mL was transferred into a 20 mL culture
423 medium in a serum bottle. These cultures were incubated at 55 °C at 100 rpm shaking until
424 reaching the exponential phase and were then ready for use. Depending on the experimental
425 setup, these seed cultures were used to inoculate a second seed in serum bottles or bioreactors.

426 **Culture media composition and preparation**

427 For glycerol stocks and seed cultures of *C. thermocellum* in serum bottles, CTFUD was used
428 as the culture medium. One liter of CTFUD consisted of 3.0 g sodium citrate tribasic
429 dihydrate, 1.3 g ammonium sulfate, 0.35 g potassium phosphate monobasic, 0.5 g L-cysteine
430 HCl, 0.13 g calcium chloride dihydrate, 2.6 g magnesium chloride hexahydrate, 0.001 g
431 ferrous sulfate heptahydrate, and vitamins including 0.02 g pyridoxamine dihydrochloride,
432 0.004 g p-aminobenzoic acid, 0.002 g D-biotin, and 0.002 g vitamin B12. Depending on the
433 experimental campaign, CTFUD was supplemented with various carbon sources. For the
434 fermentations conducted in this study, as well as for the glycerol stocks and seed cultures of
435 *C. thermobutyricum* in serum bottles, the Medium for Thermophilic Clostridia (MTC) was
436 utilized. MTC was prepared following the method described by Holwerda *et al.*, 2012, using
437 stock solutions combined with water and the desired carbon source depending on the
438 experimental campaign. The pH of all the media was adjusted to 7.0 using 2M KOH and then
439 filter-sterilized. This was done using Millipore filters (Nalgene™ Rapid-Flow™ Sterile
440 Single Use Vacuum Filter Units with PES membrane, Fisher Cat# 567-0020) or RCD (DCF
441 152/S; Andritz, Germany), both with a pore size of 0.2 μM. After sterilization, the media was
442 placed in an anaerobic chamber overnight.

443 **Seed cultures in bioreactors**

444 *C. thermocellum* seed bioreactors were prepared by combining 200 mL of deionized water
445 and 2.5 g of Avicel in each bioreactor, followed by autoclaving at 121 °C for 60 minutes.
446 Subsequently, 250 mL of 2x MTC devoid of a carbon source and filter-sterilized were added.
447 Once the bioreactors attained anaerobic conditions, pH 7.0, and a temperature of 55 °C, they
448 were inoculated with 50 mL of actively growing cultures from CTFUD serum bottles.
449 Typically, it took 10-24 hours for the seed reactors to reach the exponential growth phase,
450 signaling readiness for transfer to the experimental bioreactors. The growth state of the
451 cultures was monitored by observing base addition and visualizing the cultures under a
452 microscope. *C. thermobutyricum* seed bioreactors underwent dry autoclaving at 121 °C for
453 60 minutes. Following autoclaving, 500 mL of filter-sterilized MTC media supplemented
454 with 5 g L⁻¹ of cellobiose and 4.5 g L⁻¹ of yeast extract, was added. Upon achieving anaerobic
455 conditions, a pH of 7.0, and a temperature of 55 °C, the bioreactors were inoculated with 50
456 mL of actively growing cultures from MTC serum bottles. Typically, the seed reactors
457 required 6-8 hours to reach the exponential growth phase, signaling readiness for transfer to
458 the experimental bioreactors. Monitoring the growth status involved measuring the OD at
459 600 nm and inspecting the cultures under a microscope.

460 **Experiments in bioreactors**

461 Bioreactor experiments in this study were maintained at a temperature of 55 °C with stirring
462 at 150 rpm. Nitrogen sparging at a rate of 0.1 vvm was employed to ensure anaerobic
463 conditions. pH adjustments to 7 were made using either 2N KOH or 2N H₂SO₄, with pH
464 control during cultivations maintained using 2N KOH. Samples were aseptically collected at
465 intervals throughout the fermentation process to assess bacterial growth, acid production, and
466 sugar utilization. Unless specified otherwise, all fermentations were performed in duplicate.
467 Experimental bioreactors for *C. thermocellum* were loaded with 30 g L⁻¹ of DMR in 500 mL
468 of MTC culture media. Autoclaving was carried out with the solids and 200 mL of DI water.
469 Subsequently, 250 mL of 2x MTC devoid of a carbon source and filter-sterilized were
470 introduced. Upon achieving the desired anaerobic conditions, pH 7.0, and a temperature of
471 55 °C, the bioreactors were inoculated with 50 mL of actively growing cultures sourced from
472 seed bioreactors. *C. thermobutyricum* experimental bioreactors contained DMR liquor
473 diluted with MTC media to a total sugar concentration of 30 g L⁻¹. The bioreactors were
474 autoclaved dry at 121 °C for 60 minutes. After autoclaving, filtered-sterilized MTC media
475 without sugar and supplemented with 4.5 g L⁻¹ of yeast extract, and DMR liquor were added.
476 Once the bioreactors achieved the desired anaerobic conditions, a pH of 7.0, and a
477 temperature of 55 °C, they were inoculated with actively growing cultures from *Clostridium*
478 *thermobutyricum* seed bioreactors to an initial OD of 0.01. Co-cultures experimental
479 bioreactors contained 500 mL of MTC culture media with 30 g L⁻¹ of DMR. The bioreactors
480 were autoclaved with the solids and 200 mL of DI water. Then, 250 mL of 2x filter-sterilized
481 MTC without carbon source and supplemented with 4.5 g L⁻¹ of yeast extract were added.
482 After the bioreactors achieved the desired anaerobic conditions, pH 7.0, and temperature of

483 55 °C, they were inoculated with 50 mL of actively growing cultures from *C. thermocellum*
484 seed bioreactors, and with actively growing cultures from *C. thermobutyricum* seed
485 bioreactors to an initial OD of 0.01.

486 **Statistical methods and analysis**

487 Data were collected from two biological replicates ($n = 2$) for each experimental condition.
488 Due to the small sample size, no inferential statistical tests were performed, and error bars
489 were not included in the figures, as the statistical power is insufficient to provide reliable
490 estimates of variability. Instead, the mean values of the two replicates are presented, and
491 individual data points are plotted to transparently convey the observed variability. Growth
492 and production kinetics were predicted and characterized using the Fitteriv algorithm (Ver.
493 1.2) developed by Swain *et al.* (2016) with default parameters. The algorithm applies a
494 Gaussian fit to the raw data, and the resulting fitted curves were plotted in all cases. This
495 method effectively addresses the limitations associated with the small sample size.

496 **Data availability**

497 The data supporting this study are included within the paper and the supplementary
498 information files. A reporting summary for this article is also provided as a supplementary
499 file. Model files in were deposited within a GitHub repository:
500 <https://github.com/glastiri/Coculture>. Datasets generated and analyzed during the study are
501 available from the corresponding author upon request.

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636 08GO28308. The views and opinions of the authors expressed herein do not necessarily state
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641 represents that its use would not infringe privately owned rights.

642 **Author contribution**

643 G.L.P. and K.Z. conceived the study. M.K. helped construct the initial models' drafts. G.L.P.
644 developed individual GEM models, the CM-model and computational methods as well as
645 performed simulations and experimental designs. L.M., N.H., V.S.N. performed bioreactor
646 experiments and substrate and byproducts measurement with input from J.L and M.G.
647 Results were discussed by G.L.P, L.M., M.G. and K.Z. G.L.P. and L.M. analyzed the data.
648 G.L.P. wrote the manuscript with input from all co-authors.

649 **Competing interests**

650 The authors declare no competing interests.

651

652

653 **Fig. 1: Construction of individual and community metabolic models: process and features. a**

654 Initial draft models of *Clostridium thermocellum* (CTC) and *Clostridium thermobutyricum* (CTB)

655 were constructed using different information sources and the RAVEN Toolbox (Wang *et al.*, 2018),

656 followed by iteratively manual curation using COBRApy (Ebrahim *et al.*, 2013), and biological

657 information. **b** Key attributes of the final curated individual genome scale metabolic models (GEMs),

658 with the pie chart indicating the percentage of genomic coverage. **c** Depiction of the structure of the

659 two individual GEMs merged into a compartmentalized community metabolic model (CM-model),

660 featuring a shared metabolite pool (SMP) and a composite objective considering growth for both

661 members. **d** Overall properties of the iGL²1559 CM-model, colors in the bars represent exclusive

662 features coming from each individual GEM, while gray denotes common or shared features. **e**

663 Distribution of unique reactions across different metabolic subsystems of each individual.

664

665

666 **Fig. 2: Co-culture carbohydrate substrate uptake capabilities.** a Deacetylated and
 667 mechanically refined corn stover (DMR) average composition used in *in vivo* growth setups (left).
 668 Carbohydrate ratio used to perform growth simulations with DMR as carbon substrate (right). b
 669 Profile of experimentally measured *Clostridium thermocellum* (CTC) free soluble carbohydrate
 670 excretion after growth on DMR solids. c Profile of experimentally determined *Clostridium*
 671 *thermobutyricum* (CTB) free soluble carbohydrate consumption derived from growth on DMR liquor.
 672 d Profile of experimentally measured free soluble carbohydrate excretion/consumption for the CTC-
 673 CTB consortium using DMR solids as substrate. In all cases, circle markers indicate individual
 674 measurements obtained from independent samples (n = 2), while diamonds represent the mean. The
 675 line represents the predicted production kinetics using a Gaussian fit (see Methods). Please note the
 676 different y-axis scales in panels b-d. e *Top*: Representation of modeled carbohydrate hydrolysis and
 677 metabolism in CTC. Cellulose and hemicellulose are subjected to enzymatic degradation in the
 678 cellulosome by cellulases (CELase) and xylanases (XYLase). Hydrolyzed glucans (glucose
 679 monomers (Glu_m) ≤ 6) are transported into the cell via ABC-type transporters. Upon internalization,
 680 glucans undergo phosphorolytic cleavage by cyclodextrin phosphorylase (CDPase) to yield glucose-

681 1-phosphate (G1P) and a glucan molecule shortened by one glucose unit, iteratively reducing its
682 length until cellobiose ($\text{Glu}_m = 2$) is obtained. Cellobiose is subsequently cleaved by cellobiose
683 phosphorylase (CBPase) to produce glucose and G1P. Glucose is further converted by glucokinase
684 (Glk) to glucose-6-phosphate (G6P). G1P molecules are converted to G6P by phosphoglucomutase
685 (Pgm), which are then channeled into a GTP driven glycolytic pathway. *Bottom*: Visualization of the
686 modeled carbohydrate uptake and metabolism in CTB. Hydrolyzed glucans ($\text{Glu}_m \leq 2$) are transported
687 into the cell via ABC-type transporters. Once inside, cellobiose is split into two glucose units by
688 cellobiose hydrolase (CBHase). Glucose then gets converted to G6P by Glk and fed into the glycolytic
689 pathway. Additionally, hydrolyzed xylose is internalized via ABC-type transporters and then
690 converted into xylulose by xylose isomerase (Xi) and subsequently phosphorylated by xylulokinase
691 (Xk) to yield xylulose-5-phosphate, which follows the pentose phosphate pathway producing
692 intermediates for glycolysis. **f** Growth rates for CTC and CTB, both individually and in co-culture
693 across the various carbohydrates present in DMR. Circles represent the *in silico* predicted rates,
694 assuming a total carbon source uptake of $10 \text{ mmol gDW}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$, while triangles indicate experimentally
695 determined growth rates based on measurements from independent samples ($n = 2$), inferred using
696 time derivatives (see Methods).

697

698 **Fig. 3: Fermentation profiles of the Syn-com.** **a** *In vivo* fermentation profile of *Clostridium*
699 *thermocellum* (CTC) cultivated on mechanically refined corn stover (DMR). **b** Fermentation
700 profile of *Clostridium thermobutyricum* (CTB) during growth on DMR liquor. **c** Fermentation profile
701 of CTC-CTB co-culture grown on DMR. In all cases, circle markers indicate individual
702 measurements obtained from independent samples ($n = 2$). The line represents the predicted
703 production kinetics using a Gaussian fit (see Methods). Note the different y-axis in panels b-d. **d**
704 Predicted fermentation profiles of the community and its constituent members using *in silico*
705 simulations for hexoses (cellobiose), pentoses (xylose) and DMR (cellobiose and xylose). Color
706 intensity reflects the quantity of excreted products ($\text{mmol DW}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$). **f** Heatmap depicting the amino
707 acid (AAs) exchange among members. Green indicates AAs produced in excess by CTC and
708 consumed by CTB, while blue indicates AAs produced by CTB and consumed by CTC. Intensity of
709 color denotes the amount exchanged ($\text{mmol DW}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$). **g** Allocation of metabolic flux quantities
710 across various subsystems within the individual community members.

711

712 **Fig. 4: Dynamics of acetic acid (AA) and butyric acid (BA) production systems.** **a** Flux dynamics
 713 in BA production without AA addition. **b** Fluxomic analysis of BA biosynthesis pathways with AA
 714 (and putatively ethanol, Etoh) supplementation in the medium. **c** *In vivo* butyrate production of the
 715 co-culture across distinct proportions of AA to Etoh addition. In all cases, markers indicate individual
 716 measurements obtained from independent samples (n = 2) and the line represents the predicted
 717 production kinetics using a Gaussian fit (see Methods). **d** *In silico* assessment of BA production by
 718 the co-culture with varied concentrations and ratios of AA to Etoh. **e** Growth rate predictions of the
 719 co-culture across varied concentrations and ratios of AA to Etoh.

720

721

722 **Fig. 5: Butyric acid (BA) production bottlenecks and potential framework for optimization. a**
 723 Residual substrates and fermentation by-products of the co-culture cultivated in deacetylated and

724 mechanically refined corn stover (DMR). **b** Primary factors contributing to bottlenecks in BA
725 production. **c** Enhancing strategies proposed for co-culture augmentation.

Model ID	<i>iCBI665</i>	<i>iHN637</i>	<i>iYO844</i>	<i>iML1515</i>	<i>iGL735</i>	<i>iGL834</i>
Genes	665	637	844	1515	735	834
Reactions	795	785	1250	1877	780	876
Metabolites	854	698	990	2712	733	790
Genome Coverage	24%	15%	20%	33%	26%	27%
Microorganism	<i>Clostridium thermocellum</i>	<i>Clostridium ljungdahlii</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Clostridium thermocellum</i>	<i>Clostridium thermobutyrycum</i>
Reference	Garcia <i>et al.</i> , 2020	Nagarahan <i>et al.</i> , 2013	Oh <i>et al.</i> , 2007	Monk <i>et al.</i> , 2017	This study	This study

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727 **Table 1. Overview of the main features of the GEM models utilized and developed in this study.**